

The Bent and Hyper-Bent Properties of a Class of Boolean Functions

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Abstract—This paper considers the bent and hyper-bent properties of a class of Boolean functions. For one case, we present a detailed description for them to be hyper-bent functions, and give a necessary condition for them to be bent functions for another case.

Keywords—Boolean functions, bent functions, hyper-bent functions, character sums.

I. INTRODUCTION

BENT function is a class of Boolean functions with even variables and with the maximal distance to all affine functions. In fact, the distance of an n -variable bent function to any affine function equals $2^{n-1} - 2^{\frac{n}{2}-1}$. Bent function was introduced by Rothaus [9] in 1976, later in 2001 Youssef et al [10] found a subclass of bent functions with even better cryptographic properties, which was named as hyper-bent functions. Thanks to their applications in cryptography, coding theory and combinatorial design, many interests have been put in bent and hyper-bent functions recently [2], [3], [4], [6], [7], [8].

In this paper, we consider a class of Boolean functions defined on \mathbb{F}_{2^n} of the form:

$$f_{a,b}^{(r)}(x) := \text{Tr}_1^n(ax^{r(2^m-1)}) + \text{Tr}_1^4(bx^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}}), \quad (1)$$

where $n = 2m$, $m \equiv 2k \pmod{4}$, $k \in \{0, 1\}$, $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}$ and $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}$. When $m = 2 \pmod{4}$, with the help of the factorization of $x^5 + x + a^{-1}$ and Kloosterman sums, this paper characterizes the cases for $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ to be hyper-bent. Further more, for $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^{\frac{m}{2}}}$, we list all the hyper-bent functions of the form of $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$. When $m = 0 \pmod{4}$, we give a necessary condition for $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ to be bent.

The rest of paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we give some notations and recall some basic knowledge for this paper. Then we describe the hyper-bent properties of $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ when $m \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$ and study the bent properties of $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ when $m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$ in Section III and Section IV respectively. Finally, we conclude our work in Section V.

II. PRELIMINARIES

The **sign** function of Boolean function f is $\chi(f) := (-1)^f$.

Definition 1: A Boolean function $f : \mathbb{F}_{2^n} \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_2$ is called a bent function, if $\widehat{\chi}_f(w) = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}} (-1)^{f(x) + \text{Tr}_1^n(wx)} =$

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$\pm 2^{\frac{n}{2}}$ ($\forall w \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}$), where Tr_1^n is the absolute trace function defined as $\text{Tr}_1^n(x) := x + x^2 + x^{2^2} + \dots + x^{2^{n-1}}$.

Hyper-bent function is an important subclass of bent functions defined as

Definition 2: A bent function $f : \mathbb{F}_{2^n} \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_2$ is called a hyper-bent function, if, for any i satisfying $(i, 2^n - 1) = 1$, $f(x^i)$ is also a bent function.

Charpin and Gong [4] gave the following property to determine a hyper-bent function.

Proposition 1: Let $n = 2m$, α be a primitive element of \mathbb{F}_{2^n} and f be a Boolean function over \mathbb{F}_{2^n} satisfying $f(\alpha^{2^{m+1}}x) = f(x)$ ($\forall x \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}$) and $f(0) = 0$. Let ξ be a primitive $2^m + 1$ -th root in $\mathbb{F}_{2^n}^*$. Then f is a hyper-bent function if and only if the cardinality of the set $\{i | f(\xi^i) = 1, 0 \leq i \leq 2^m\}$ is 2^{m-1} .

Kloosterman sum is a powerful tool to study the hyper-bent properties of some classes of boolean functions.

Kloosterman sums on \mathbb{F}_{2^n} are defined as

$$K_m(a) := \sum_{x \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^m(ax + \frac{1}{x})), \quad a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}.$$

Some properties of Kloosterman sums are given by the following proposition.

Proposition 2: ([5], Theorem 3.4) Let $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$. Then $K_m(a) \in [1 - 2^{(m+2)/2}, 1 + 2^{(m+2)/2}]$ and $4 \mid K_m(a)$.

Quintic Weil sums on \mathbb{F}_{2^m} are

$$Q_m(a) := \sum_{x \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^m(a(x^5 + x^3 + x))), \quad a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}.$$

And the value of $Q_m(a)$ is related to the factorization of the polynomial $P(x) = x^5 + x + a^{-1}$ [1].

When $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^{2m_1}}$, $m = 2m_1$, $K_m(a)$ and $Q_m(a)$ have the following properties

Proposition 3: (Lemma 3 [1]) If $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^{2m_1}}$, $m = 2m_1$,

(1) $1 - K_m(a) = (1 - K_{m_1}(a))^2 - 2 \cdot 2^{m_1}$.

(2) if $m_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, then $Q_m(a) \in \{0, 2 \cdot 2^{m/2}, -4 \cdot 2^{m/2}\}$.

Proposition 4: [11] The Ramanujan-Nagell equation $x^2 - D = 2^{n+2}$ has at most 4 solutions (x, n) , which are

$$(x, n) := (2^k - 3, 1), (2^k - 1, k), (2^k + 1, k + 1), (3 \cdot 2^k - 1, 2k + 1),$$

where $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and $D \in \mathbb{N}$ is odd.

With the help of the solutions of Ramanujan-Nagell equation,

Lemma 1: If $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^{2m_1}}$, $m = 2m_1$, $m_1 > 1$, then $K_m(a) \neq -4$.

Proof: By Proposition 3, if $K_m(a) = -4$,

$$(1 - K_{m_1}(a))^2 = 2 \cdot 2^{m_1} + 5. \quad (2)$$

It is easy to check that when $m_1 < 5$, $2 \cdot 2^{m_1} + 5$ is not a square. By Proposition 4, (2) has at most 4 solutions ($| (1 - K_{m_1}(a)) |, n$), which are

$$(| (1 - K_{m_1}(a)) |, m_1 - 1) = (2^k - 3, 1), (2^k - 1, k), (2^k + 1, k + 1), (3 \cdot 2^k - 1, 2k + 1),$$

where $k \in \mathbb{N}$. We can check all the 4 solutions can not satisfy (2). For example, if $(| (1 - K_{m_1}(a)) |, m_1 - 1) = (3 \cdot 2^k - 1, 2k + 1)$, then

$$(3 \cdot 2^k - 1)^2 = 2^{2k+1+2} + 5. \quad (3)$$

When $k = 1, 2$, $(3 \cdot 2^k - 1)^2 \neq 2^{2k+1+2} + 5$. When $k \geq 3$, $(3 \cdot 2^k - 1)^2 > 2^{2k+1+2} + 5$. Thus (3) has no integral solution, therefore (2) has no integral solution either, which concludes the proof. ■

III. THE HYPER-BENT PROPERTY OF $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ WHEN $m = 2 \pmod{4}$

In this section, we consider the Boolean function $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ defined by (1), where $n = 2m$, $m \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}$ and $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}$. As the cyclotomic coset of 2 module $2^n - 1$ containing $\frac{2^n - 1}{5}$ is

$$\left\{ \frac{2^n - 1}{5}, 2 \cdot \frac{2^n - 1}{5}, 2^2 \cdot \frac{2^n - 1}{5}, 2^3 \cdot \frac{2^n - 1}{5} \right\}.$$

Its size is 4, or $o(\frac{2^n - 1}{5}) = 4$, which means $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is neither in the class considered by Charpin and Gong [4] nor in the class studied by Mesanager [6], [7].

Let α be a primitive element of \mathbb{F}_{2^n} , $\beta = \alpha^{\frac{2^n - 1}{5}}$, $\xi = \alpha^{2^m - 1}$, $U = \langle \xi \rangle$, $V = \langle \xi^5 \rangle$. Since $5 | (2^m + 1)$, V is the subgroup of U and $\#V = \frac{2^m + 1}{5}$.

For any $i \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$, define

$$\begin{aligned} S_i &= \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a \xi^{i(2^m - 1)v})) \\ &= \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a \xi^{-2i}v)) = \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a \xi^{-5i+3i}v)) \\ &= \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a \xi^{3i}v)). \quad (as \xi^{-5i} \in V) \end{aligned}$$

From the definition of S_i ,

$$S_i = S_{i \pmod{5}}. \quad (4)$$

To study the hyper-bent properties of $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$, we define the following character sum

$$\Lambda_r(a, b) := \sum_{u \in U} \chi(f_{a,b}^{(r)}(u)). \quad (5)$$

Similar to the proof of Proposition 9 in [1], the hyper-bent properties of $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ can be described as

Proposition 5: $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is a hyper-bent function if and only if $\Lambda_r(a, b) = 1$.

Before our work on $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$, let us consider a general case of $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ which is defined as

$$f_{a,b}^{(r,k)} := \text{Tr}_1^n(ax^{r(2^m - 1)}) + \text{Tr}_1^4(bx^k \frac{2^n - 1}{5}), \quad (6)$$

where a, b is defined as above and $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

When $k \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, $f_{a,b}^{(r,k)} = \text{Tr}_1^n(ax^{r(2^m - 1)}) + \text{Tr}_1^4(b)$ is a special case studied by Charpin and Gong in [4]. In this paper we only consider the case of $k \not\equiv 0 \pmod{5}$.

Proposition 6: The hyper-bent properties of $f_{a,b}^{(r,k)}$ can be represented by that of $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ efficiently, where $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}$, $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}$, $k \not\equiv 0 \pmod{5}$.

Proof: For $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}^*$, b can be written as $b = \omega \beta^j$, where $\omega^3 = 1$, $0 \leq j \leq 4$. Thus

$$\text{Tr}_1^4(bx^k \frac{2^n - 1}{5}) = \text{Tr}_1^4(\omega \beta^j x^k \frac{2^n - 1}{5}) = \text{Tr}_1^4(\omega (\beta^{\frac{j}{k}} x^{\frac{2^n - 1}{5}})^k).$$

It is easy to check,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tr}_1^4(\omega x^{\frac{2^n - 1}{5}}) &= \text{Tr}_1^4(\omega^2 x^{\frac{2^n - 1}{5}}) \\ &= \text{Tr}_1^4(\omega x^{\frac{2^n - 1}{5}}) = \text{Tr}_1^4(\omega^2 x^{\frac{2^n - 1}{5}}). \end{aligned}$$

Then $\text{Tr}_1^4(bx^k \frac{2^n - 1}{5}) = \text{Tr}_1^4(b' x^{\frac{2^n - 1}{5}})$, where $b' \in \mathbb{F}_{16}^*$.

Hence the result stands. ■

A step further, $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ has following proposition.

Proposition 7: Let $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ be defined as (1) and $(r, 5) = 1$, then $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is a hyper-bent function if and only if $f_{a',b'}^{(r)}$ is a hyper-bent one, where $a = a' \xi^i \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}$, $a' \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$, $b, b' = b \alpha^{-\frac{i}{r} \frac{2^n - 1}{5}} \in \mathbb{F}_{16}$.

Proof: Notice that $\forall a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}$, $a = a' \xi^i$, where $a' \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$, $\xi = \alpha^{2^m - 1}$ is a primitive $2^m + 1$ -th root of unity in \mathbb{F}_{2^n} and $0 \leq i \leq 2^m$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} f_{a,b}^{(r)}(x) &= \text{Tr}_1^n(ax^{r(2^m - 1)}) + \text{Tr}_1^4(bx^{\frac{2^n - 1}{5}}) \\ &= \text{Tr}_1^n(a' (\alpha^{\frac{i}{r}} x)^{r(2^m - 1)}) + \text{Tr}_1^4(b \alpha^{-\frac{i}{r} \frac{2^n - 1}{5}} (\alpha^{\frac{i}{r}} x)^{\frac{2^n - 1}{5}}) \\ &= f_{a',b'}^{(r)}(\alpha^{-\frac{i}{r}} x), \end{aligned}$$

where $b' = b \alpha^{-\frac{i}{r} \frac{2^n - 1}{5}} \in \mathbb{F}_{16}$.

Thus $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is linearly equivalent to $f_{a',b'}^{(r)}$, that is to say, $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is a hyper-bent function if and only if $f_{a',b'}^{(r)}$ is a hyper-bent one. ■

By Proposition 7, if $a = a' \xi^i$, and $\beta = \alpha^{\frac{2^n - 1}{5}}$, we have the following results

- $f_{a,b}^{(1)}$ is linearly equivalent to $f_{a',b\beta^{4i}}^{(1)}$.
- $f_{a,b}^{(2)}$ is linearly equivalent to $f_{a',b\beta^{2i}}^{(2)}$.
- $f_{a,b}^{(3)}$ is linearly equivalent to $f_{a',b\beta^{3i}}^{(3)}$.
- $f_{a,b}^{(4)}$ is linearly equivalent to $f_{a',b\beta^i}^{(4)}$.

By Proposition 7 and Proposition 6, when $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}$, the hyper-bent properties of $f_{a,b}^{(r,k)}$ can be fully represented by that of $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$, where $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$, $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}$. Since the hyper-bent properties of $f_{a,b}^{(1)}$ had been studied elaborately in [1], in the following parts of this Section we only consider the rest cases of r .

A. The Case of $r = 5$

1) The hyper-bent properties of $f_{a,b}^{(5)}$, where $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$:

Proposition 8: Let $n = 2m$ and $m \equiv \pm 2, \pm 6 \pmod{20}$, If $b \in \{0\} \cup \{\beta^i | i = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$, then the Boolean function

$f_{a,b}^{(5)}$ is not a hyper-bent function. Further, if $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}^* \setminus \{\beta^i | 0 \leq i \leq 4\}$, $f_{a,b}^{(5)}$ is a hyper-bent function if and only if

$$\sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(av)) = 1.$$

Proof: By (5),

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_5(a, b) &= \sum_{u \in U} \chi(f_{a,b}^{(5)}(u)) \\ &= \sum_{u \in U} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(au^{5(2^m-1)})) \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(bu^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}})). \end{aligned}$$

Notice that $U = \langle \xi \rangle$, $V = \langle \xi^5 \rangle$ and $U = \xi^0 V \cup \xi^1 V \cup \xi^2 V \cup \xi^3 V \cup \xi^4 V$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_5(a, b) &= \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b(\xi^i v)^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a(\xi^i v)^{5(2^m-1)})) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b(\xi^i v)^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a(\xi^{5i})^{2^m-1} v^{5(2^m-1)})) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Since $(\xi^{5i})^{2^m-1} \in V$ and $m \equiv \pm 2, \pm 6 \pmod{20}$, $(5(2^m-1), \#V) = (5, \frac{2^m+1}{5}) = 1$. Then $v \mapsto (\xi^{5i})^{2^m-1} v^{5(2^m-1)}$ is a permutation of V . Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_5(a, b) &= \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b(\xi^i v)^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(av)) \\ &= (\sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\xi^{i\frac{2^n-1}{5}}))) (\sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(av))). \end{aligned}$$

As $\xi^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}} = (\alpha^{2^m-1})^{\frac{(2^m-1)(2^m+1)}{5}} = \beta^{2^m-1} = \beta^{2^m+1-2} = \beta^3$,

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_5(a, b) &= (\sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^{3i}))) (\sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(av))) \\ &= (\sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^i))) (\sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(av))). \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

By (9), when $b = 0$, $\Lambda_5(a, 0) = 5 \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(av))$, and thus $\Lambda_5(a, 0) \neq 1$. By Proposition 5, $f_{a,0}^{(5)}$ is not a hyper-bent function.

When $b \neq 0$, b can be represented as $b = \omega\beta^j$, where $\omega^3 = 1$ and $0 \leq j \leq 4$. Then

$$\sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^i)) = \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(\omega\beta^{i+j})) = \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(\omega\beta^i)). \quad (10)$$

Since $\omega^3 = 1$ and $\omega^4 = \omega$, we have

$$\text{Tr}_1^4(\omega\beta^i) = \text{Tr}_1^4(\omega^4\beta^{4i}) = \text{Tr}_1^4(\omega\beta^{4i}).$$

If $\omega = 1$, $\sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^i)) = \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(\beta^i))$. As β satisfies $\beta^4 + \beta^3 + \beta^2 + \beta + 1 = 0$, $\text{Tr}_1^4(\beta^i) = 1, i \neq 0$. Then

$$\sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^i)) = -3. \text{ Therefore,}$$

$$\Lambda_5(a, b) = -3 \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(av)), b = \beta^j, 0 \leq j \leq 4.$$

By Proposition 5, $f_{a,\beta^j}^{(5)}$ is not a hyper-bent function. When $\omega \neq 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tr}_1^4(\omega\beta) + \text{Tr}_1^4(\omega\beta^2) &= \text{Tr}_1^4(\omega(\beta + \beta^2)) \\ &= \omega(\beta + \beta^2 + \beta^3 + \beta^4) + \omega^2(\beta + \beta^2 + \beta^3 + \beta^4) \\ &= 1. \end{aligned}$$

Then $\chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(\omega\beta)) + \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(\omega\beta^2)) = 0$. Similarly, $\chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(\omega\beta^3)) + \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(\omega\beta^4)) = 0$. Therefore,

$$\Lambda_5(a, b) = \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(av)), b = \omega\beta^j, 0 \leq j \leq 4, \omega^3 = 1, \omega \neq 1.$$

By Proposition 5, the second part of this proposition follows. ■

In Proposition 8, we consider the hyper-bent properties of the Boolean function $f_{a,b}^{(5)}$ for $m \equiv \pm 2, \pm 6 \pmod{20}$. The proposition below discusses the hyper-bent properties of $f_{a,b}^{(5)}$ for $m \equiv 10 \pmod{20}$.

Proposition 9: Let $n = 2m$, $m \equiv 10 \pmod{20}$, $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$, $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}$. then the Boolean function $f_{a,b}^{(5)}$ is not a hyper-bent function.

Proof: Notice that $\Lambda_5(a, b) = \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\xi^{i\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a(\xi^{5i})^{2^m-1} v^{5(2^m-1)}))$. Since $m \equiv 10 \pmod{20}$, $25 | (2^m + 1)$ and $(5(2^m - 1), \frac{2^m+1}{5}) = 5$. Then $v \mapsto v^{5(2^m-1)}$ is a 5 to 1 morphism from V to $V^5 := \{v^5 | v \in V\}$. Therefore,

$$\Lambda_5(a, b) = 5 \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{v \in V^5} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\xi^{i\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a(\xi^{5i})^{2^m-1} v)).$$

Hence, $5 | \Lambda_5(a, b)$ and $\Lambda_5(a, b)$ is not equal to 1, By Proposition 5, $f_{a,b}^{(5)}$ is not a hyper-bent function. ■

By Proposition 8,

$$\sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(av)) = \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(av^{2^m-1})).$$

Notice that $\sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(av)) = S_0$ in [1]. By Proposition 15 in [1],

$$\sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(av)) = \frac{1}{5} [1 - K_m(a) + 2Q_m(a)]. \quad (11)$$

Further, By Proposition 16 and 18 in [1], we have the following results.

Proposition 10: Let $n = 2m$, $m \equiv \pm 2, \pm 6 \pmod{20}$, $m \geq 6$ and $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}^* \setminus \{\beta^i | 0 \leq i \leq 4\}$, then $f_{a,b}^{(5)}$ is a hyper-bent function if and only if one of the assertions (1) and (2) holds.

- (1) $Q_m(a) = 0$, $K_m(a) = -4$.
- (2) $Q_m(a) = 2^{m-1}$, $K_m(a) = 2 \cdot 2^{m-1} - 4$.

2) The hyper-bent properties of $f_{a,b}^{(5)}$ where $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$: In this part, we always assume $n = 2m$, $m = 2m_1$, $m_1 \in \mathbb{N}$.

Lemma 2: Let $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}^*$, $\gamma \in \{z \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m} : z^5 = 1, z \neq 1\} = \alpha^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}}, \text{ then}$

$$\sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\gamma^i)) = \begin{cases} 1, & b^5 \neq 1 \\ -3, & b^5 = 1. \end{cases}$$

Proof: Firstly, if $b^5 = 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\gamma^i)) &= \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(\gamma^i)) = 1 + \sum_{i=0}^3 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(\gamma^{2^i})) \\ &= 1 + 4\chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(\gamma)) = -3. \end{aligned}$$

Secondly, if $b^5 \neq 1$,

$$\sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\gamma^i)) = \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b^2\gamma^{2^i})) = \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b^2\gamma^i)).$$

Since $\forall b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}^*$, $b = \omega^j \gamma^i$, $0 \leq j \leq 2$, $0 \leq i \leq 4$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}^*} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b)) &= 1 + \sum_{b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}^*} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b)) \\ &= 1 + \sum_{j=0}^2 \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(\omega^j \gamma^i)) \\ &= 1 + \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(\gamma^i)) + \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(\omega \gamma^i)) + \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(\omega^2 \gamma^i)) \\ &= 1 + (-3) + 2 \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(\omega \gamma^i)). \end{aligned}$$

Notice that $\sum_{b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}^*} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b)) = 0$, hence $\sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\gamma^i)) = 1$, and the conclusion stands. ■

Theorem 1: If $a = a' \xi^i$, $a' \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$, the hyper-bent properties of $f_{a,b}^{(5)}$ can be described as follows:

- (1) when $m \equiv 10 \pmod{20}$, $f_{a,b}^{(5)}$ is not hyper-bent.
- (2) when $m \equiv \pm 2, \pm 6 \pmod{20}$, $f_{a,b}^{(5)}$ is hyper-bent if and only if $S_{2i} = 1$.

Proof: To the character sum of $f_{a,b}^{(5)}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda(a' \xi^i, b) &= \sum_{u \in U} \chi(f_{a' \xi^i, b}^{(5)}(u)) \\ &= \sum_{u \in U} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a' \xi^i u^{5(2^m-1)}) \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(bu^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^4 \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a' \xi^i (\xi^j v)^{5(2^m-1)}) \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b(\xi^j v)^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^4 \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b \xi^j \frac{2^n-1}{5})) \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a' \xi^i \xi^{5j(2^m-1)} v^{5(2^m-1)})). \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

If $m \equiv 10 \pmod{20}$, then $(5, \#V) = 5$. By (12), $\Lambda(a' \xi^i, b) = 5 \sum_{j=0}^4 \sum_{v' \in V^5} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b \xi^j \frac{2^n-1}{5})) \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a' \xi^i \xi^{5j(2^m-1)} v'))$, where $V^5 = \{v^5 \mid v \in V\}$, $v \mapsto v^{5(2^m-1)}$ is a 5 to 1

morphism from V to V^5 . Thus $\Lambda(a' \xi^i, b) \neq 1$, and $f_{a,b}^{(5)}$ is not a hyper-bent function.

If $m \equiv \pm 2, \pm 6 \pmod{20}$, then $(5, \#V) = 1$. By (12) and (9),

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda(a' \xi^i, b) &= \sum_{j=0}^4 \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^j)) \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a' \xi^i v)) \\ &= \left(\sum_{j=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^j)) \right) \left(\sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a' (\xi^{\frac{i}{2^m-1}})^{2^m-1} v)) \right), \end{aligned}$$

where $\beta = \alpha^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}}$, $\xi^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}} = \beta^3$. Since $\frac{1}{2^m-1} \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$, then by (4),

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda(a' \xi^i, b) &= \left(\sum_{j=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^j)) \right) \left(\sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a' (\xi^{2i})^{2^m-1} v)) \right) \\ &= \left(\sum_{j=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^j)) \right) S_{2i}. \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 2,

$$\Lambda(a' \xi^i, b) = \begin{cases} S_{2i}, & b^5 \neq 1 \\ -3S_{2i}, & b^5 = 1. \end{cases}$$

If $b^5 = 1$, $3 \mid \Lambda(a' \xi^i, b)$. Thus $f_{a' \xi^i, b}^{(5)}$ is not a hyper-bent function.

If $b^5 \neq 1$, then $f_{a' \xi^i, b}^{(5)}$ is a hyper-bent function if and only if $S_{2i} = 1$. ■

B. The Case of $r = 2$

When $b = 0$, the hyper-bent propriety of $f_{a,0}^{(2)}$ has been studied by Canteaut et al in [2]. We consider the case of $b \neq 0$.

Proposition 11: Let $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$, $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}^*$, we have

- (1) if $b = 1$, then $\Lambda_2(a, b) = S_0 - 2(S_1 + S_2) = 2S_0 - \Lambda_2(a, 0)$.
- (2) if $b \in \{\beta + \beta^2, \beta + \beta^3, \beta^2 + \beta^4, \beta^3 + \beta^4\}$, then $\Lambda_2(a, b) = S_0$.
- (3) if $b = \beta$ or β^4 , then $\Lambda_2(a, b) = -S_0 - 2S_2$.
- (4) if $b = \beta^2$ or β^3 , then $\Lambda_2(a, b) = -S_0 - 2S_1$.
- (5) if $b = 1 + \beta$ or $1 + \beta^4$, then $\Lambda_2(a, b) = -S_0 + 2S_2$.
- (6) if $b = 1 + \beta^2$ or $1 + \beta^3$, then $\Lambda_2(a, b) = -S_0 + 2S_1$.
- (7) if $b = \beta + \beta^4$, then $\Lambda_2(a, b) = S_0 + 2S_2 - 2S_1$.
- (8) if $b = \beta^2 + \beta^3$, then $\Lambda_2(a, b) = S_0 - 2S_2 + 2S_1$.

Proof: Similar to proof of Proposition 13 in [1] the results hold. ■

Corollary 1: Let $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$, $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}^*$, we have

- (1) $f_{a,b}^{(2)}$ holds the same hyper-bent proprieties as $f_{a,b^2}^{(1)}$.
- (2) if b satisfies $(b+1)(b^4+b+1) = 0$, then $f_{a,b}^{(2)}$ holds the same hyper-bent proprieties as $f_{a,b}^{(1)}$.

Proof: (1) By Proposition 11 and Proposition 13 in [1],

$$\Lambda_2(a, b) = \Lambda_1(a, b^2).$$

Hence $f_{a,b}^{(2)}$ is a hyper-bent function if and only if $f_{a,b^2}^{(1)}$ is.

- (2) Similarly, if b satisfying $(b+1)(b^4+b+1) = 0$, then,

$$\Lambda_2(a, b) = \Lambda_1(a, b).$$

Thus $f_{a,b}^{(2)}$ holds the same hyper-bent proprieties as $f_{a,b}^{(1)}$. ■

C. The General Case of r

Theorem 2: Let $n = 2m$, $m \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$ and $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}$. If $(r, \frac{2^m+1}{5}) > 1$, then $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is not a hyper-bent function. Further, if $(r, \frac{2^m+1}{5}) = 1$, then

- (1) If $r \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, then $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ and $f_{a,b}^{(5)}$ has the same hyper-bent properties.
- (2) If $r \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{5}$, then $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ and $f_{a,b}^{(1)}$ has the same hyper-bent properties.
- (3) If $r \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$, then $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ and $f_{a,b}^{(2)}$ has the same hyper-bent properties.

Proof: Notice that

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_r(a, b) &= \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b(\xi^i v)^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a(\xi^i v)^{r(2^m-1)})) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\xi^{i\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a\xi^{ri(2^m-1)} v^{r(2^m-1)})). \end{aligned}$$

Let $d = (r(2^m - 1), \#V) = (r, \frac{2^m+1}{5})$, then $\Lambda_r(a, b) = d \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\xi^{i\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \sum_{v \in V^d} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a\xi^{ri(2^m-1)} v^{r(2^m-1)}))$, where $V^d = \{v^d | v \in V\}$. If $d = (r, \frac{2^m+1}{5}) > 1$, $d|\Lambda_r(a, b)$ and $\Lambda_r(a, b) \neq 1$. Hence, $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is not a hyper-bent function.

When $d = (r, \frac{2^m+1}{5}) = 1$,

$$\Lambda_r(a, b) = \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\xi^{i\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a\xi^{ri(2^m-1)} v)). \tag{13}$$

If $r \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, from $\xi^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}} = \beta^3$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_r(a, b) &= \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^{3i})) \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a\xi^{ri(2^m-1)} v)) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^i)) \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(av)). \end{aligned}$$

Then $\Lambda_r(a, b) = \Lambda_5(a, b)$. Therefore, $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ and $f_{a,b}^{(5)}$ has the same hyper-bent properties.

If $r \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$, then

$$\Lambda_r(a, b) = \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\xi^{i\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a\xi^{i(2^m-1)} v)).$$

By Proposition 10 in [1], $\Lambda_r(a, b) = \Lambda_1(a, b)$. Hence, $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ and $f_{a,b}^{(1)}$ has the same hyper-bent properties.

If $r \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_r(a, b) &= \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\xi^{i\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a\xi^{2i(2^m-1)} v)) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^{3i})) S_{2i} \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^{9i})) S_{6i} = \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^{4i})) S_i. \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 1 in [1],

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_r(a, b) &= \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b)) S_0 + (\chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta)) + \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^4))) S_1 \\ &\quad + (\chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^2)) + \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^3))) S_2. \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Hence, $\Lambda_r(a, b) = \Lambda_2(a, b)$. $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ and $f_{a,b}^{(2)}$ has the same hyper-bent properties.

If $r \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_r(a, b) &= \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\xi^{i\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a\xi^{3i(2^m-1)} v)) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^{3i})) S_{3i} = \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^i)) S_i. \end{aligned}$$

From Lemma 1 in [1],

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_r(a, b) &= \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b)) S_0 + (\chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta)) + \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^4))) S_1 \\ &\quad + (\chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^2)) + \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^3))) S_2. \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Hence, $\Lambda_r(a, b) = \Lambda_3(a, b)$. From (14) and (15), we have $\Lambda_2(a, b) = \Lambda_3(a, b)$. Thus, $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ and $f_{a,b}^{(2)}$ have the same hyper-bent properties.

Similarly, if $r \equiv 4 \pmod{5}$, then $\Lambda_r(a, b) = \Lambda_4(a, b) = \Lambda_1(a, b)$. Thus, $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ and $f_{a,b}^{(1)}$ have the same hyper-bent properties.

Above all, the results stand. ■

From the above discussion, we have the following results on $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$.

Proposition 12: Let $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$ and $(r, \frac{2^m+1}{5}) = 1$, then

(1) If $\frac{1}{5}[1 - K_m(a) + 2Q_m(a)] = 1$, then the following Boolean functions

- (a) $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$, $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}^* \setminus \{\beta^i | i = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$, $r \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$.
- (b) $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$, $r \not\equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, $b^4 + b + 1 = 0$.

are hyper-bent functions.

(2) If $-\frac{1}{5}[3(1 - K_m(a)) - 4Q_m(a)] = 1$, then the Boolean function $f_{a,1}^{(r)}$ ($r \not\equiv 0 \pmod{5}$) is a hyper-bent function.

Proof: By Theorem 2, (11), Proposition 8 and Proposition 16 in [1], this proposition follows. ■

With Proposition 12, we can generalize Theorem 3 in [1] to the following theorem.

Theorem 3: Let $n = 2m$, $m = 2m_1$, $m_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, $m_1 \geq 3$ and $(r, \frac{2^m+1}{5}) = 1$, If one of two assertions (1) and (2) holds,

(1) $p(x) = x^5 + x + a^{-1}$ over \mathbb{F}_{2^m} is (1)(2)² and $K_m(a) = -4$.

(2) $p(x) = x^5 + x + a^{-1}$ is irreducible over \mathbb{F}_{2^m} . The quadratic form $q(x) = \text{Tr}_1^m(x(ax^4 + ax^2 + a^2x))$ over \mathbb{F}_{2^m} is even. $K_m(a) = 2 \cdot 2^{m_1} - 4$.

Then the Boolean functions

- (a) $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$, $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}^* \setminus \{\beta^i | i = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$, $r \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$.
- (b) $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$, $r \not\equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, $b^4 + b + 1 = 0$.

are hyper-bent functions.

Proof: By Proposition 16 and Theorem 3 in [1] and Proposition 12, this theorem follows. ■

By Proposition 16, Proposition 12 and Theorem 2 in [1], we have the following results for the hyper-bent properties of $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$:

Theorem 4: Let $n = 2m$, $m = 2m_1$, $m_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, $m_1 \geq 3$, $(r, \frac{2^m+1}{5}) = 1$ and $r \not\equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, then $f_{a,1}^{(r)}$ is a hyper-bent function if and only if the following assertions holds.

- (1) $p(x) = x^5 + x + a^{-1}$ is irreducible over \mathbb{F}_{2^m} .
- (2) The quadratic form $q(x) = \text{Tr}_1^m(x(ax^4 + ax^2 + a^2x))$ over \mathbb{F}_{2^m} is even.
- (3) $K_m(a) = \frac{4}{3}(2 - 2^{m_1})$.

If $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^{\frac{m}{2}}}$, the hyper-bent properties of $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is

Theorem 5: Let $n = 2m$, $m = 2m_1$, $m_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$ and $m_1 \geq 3$. If $n \neq 12, 28$, any Boolean function in

$$\{f_{a,b}^{(r)} | a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^{\frac{m}{2}}}, b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}\} \quad (16)$$

is not a hyper-bent function. Further, if $n = 12$, all the hyper-bent functions in (16) are $\text{Tr}_1^{12}(ax^{r(2^6-1)}) + \text{Tr}_1^4(bx^{\frac{2^{12}-1}{5}})$, where $r \not\equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, $(r, \frac{2^m+1}{5}) = 1$, $(a+1)(a^3+a^2+1) = 0$ and $b = \beta^i, i = 1, 2, 3, 4$. If $n = 28$, all the hyper-bent functions in (16) are $\text{Tr}_1^{28}(ax^{r(2^{14}-1)}) + \text{Tr}_1^4(bx^{\frac{2^{28}-1}{5}})$, where $r \not\equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, $(r, \frac{2^m+1}{5}) = 1$, $(a+1)(a^7+a^6+a^5+a^4+a^3+a^2+1) = 0$ and $b = \beta^i, i = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

Proof: Notice that $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^{\frac{m}{2}}}$. By Theorem 2, if $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is a hyper-bent function, $(r, \frac{2^m+1}{5}) = 1$.

Suppose $(r, \frac{2^m+1}{5}) = 1$. we first prove that $f_{a,0}^{(r)}$ is not a hyper-bent function when $r \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$. By Theorem 2, $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is a hyper-bent function if and only if $f_{a,b}^{(5)}$ is a hyper-bent function. If $b = 0$,

$$\Lambda_5(a, 0) = \sum_{u \in U} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(au^{5(2^m-1)})) = 5 \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(av^{2^m-1})).$$

Hence, $5 | \Lambda_5(a, 0)$ and $\Lambda_5(a, 0) \neq 1$. Therefore, $f_{a,0}^{(5)}$ is not a hyper-bent function. Then $f_{a,0}^{(r)}$ is not a hyper-bent function.

When $b \neq 0$, by Theorem 3, $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is a hyper-bent function if and only if $f_{a,b'}^{(1)}$ ($b'^4 + b' + 1 = 0$) is a hyper-bent function. By Theorem 5 in [1], $f_{a,b'}^{(1)}$ ($b'^4 + b' + 1 = 0$) is not a hyper-bent function. Hence, $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is not a hyper-bent function when $r \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$.

Now we discuss the case $r \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{5}$ and $(r, \frac{2^m+1}{5}) = 1$. By Theorem 2, $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is a hyper-bent function if and only if $f_{a,b}^{(1)}$ is a hyper-bent function. By Theorem 5 in [1], there are only two cases. The first case is $n = 12$, where a and b satisfy

$$(a+1)(a^3+a^2+1) = 0, b = \beta^i, i = 1, 2, 3, 4.$$

The second case is $n = 28$, where a and b satisfy

$$(a+1)(a^7+a^6+a^5+a^4+a^3+a^2+1) = 0, b = \beta^i, i = 1, 2, 3, 4.$$

When $r \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$ and $(r, \frac{2^m+1}{5}) = 1$, we have similar results.

Above all, this theorem follows. ■

IV. THE BENT PROPERTY OF $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ WHEN $m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$

In this section we consider the bent properties of $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$, where $m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}$, $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}$.

Proposition 13: Let $a = a' \xi^k \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}^*$, $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}^*$, $a' \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}^*$, $0 \leq k \leq 2^m$, $m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, $m = 2m_1$. One necessary condition for $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ to be a bent function is: $(r, 2^m + 1) = 1$, $a' \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m} \setminus \mathbb{F}_{2^{m_1}}$, $b^5 \neq 1$, $\widehat{\chi}_{f_{a,b}^{(r)}}(0) = 2^m$ and $K_m(a') = -4$.

Proof: Notice that $\forall x \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}^*$, $x = yu$, where $y \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}^*$, $u \in U = \langle \alpha^{2^m-1} \rangle$. Since $m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, $5 | 2^m - 1$.

Thus $u^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}} = (u^{2^m+1})^{\frac{2^m-1}{5}} = 1$. Now, consider the Walsh spectrum of $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ at 0, which is

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\chi}_{f_{a,b}^{(r)}}(0) &= \sum_{x \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}} \chi(f_{a,b}^{(r)}(x)) = 1 + \sum_{u \in U} \sum_{y \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}^*} \chi(f_{a,b}^{(r)}(yu)) \\ &= 1 + \sum_{u \in U} \sum_{y \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}^*} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a(yu)^{r(2^m-1)})) \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b(yu)^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \\ &= 1 + \sum_{u \in U} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(au^{r(2^m-1)})) \sum_{y \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}^*} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(by^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$\mathbb{F}_{2^m}^*$ can be written as $\mathbb{F}_{2^m}^* = \bigcup_{i=0}^4 \beta^i V$, where $V = \{z^5 | z \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}^*\}$, $\beta \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}^* \setminus V$.

If $(r(2^m - 1), 2^m + 1) = 1$, by (17),

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\chi}_{f_{a,b}^{(r)}}(0) &= 1 + \sum_{u \in U} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a' \xi^k u^{r(2^m-1)})) \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b(v\beta^i)^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \\ &= 1 + \sum_{u \in U} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a' u)) \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\beta^i \frac{2^n-1}{5})) \\ &= 1 + \sum_{u \in U} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(a' u)) \sum_{v \in V} \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\gamma^i)) \\ &= 1 + (1 - K_m(a')) \frac{2^m - 1}{5} \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\gamma^i)), \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

$(r(2^m - 1), 2^m + 1) = 1$, $u \mapsto \xi^k u^{r(2^m-1)}$ is a permutation in U , $\sum_{u \in U} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(au^{2^m-1})) = 1 - K_m(a)$. $\gamma = \beta^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}} \neq 1$ is a 5-th primitive root of unity in \mathbb{F}_{2^n} . If $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is a bent function,

$$\widehat{\chi}_{f_{a,b}^{(r)}}(0) = 1 + (K_m(a') - 1) \left(\frac{2^m - 1}{5}\right) \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\gamma^i)) = \pm 2^m.$$

By Lemma 2,

(1) if $\sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\gamma^i)) = -3$, then $K_m(a') = \frac{8}{3}$ or $3(2^m - 1)(K_m(a') - 1) = -5(2^m + 1)$. Since $K_m(a')$ is an integer, however $(\frac{2^m-1}{5}, 2^m + 1) = 1$, Neither of the two equations stands, thus $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is not a bent function.

(2) if $\sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\gamma^i)) = 1$, which means $K_m(a') = -4$, $\widehat{\chi}_{f_{a,b}^{(r)}}(0) = 2^m$, or $(2^m - 1)(K_m(a') - 1) = 5(2^m + 1)$, $\widehat{\chi}_{f_{a,b}^{(r)}}(0) = -2^m$. Since $(\frac{2^m-1}{5}, 2^m + 1) = 1$, the last group of equations can not stand. By Lemma 1, if $a' \in \mathbb{F}_{2^{m_1}}$, then $K_m(a') \neq -4$.

If $(r(2^m - 1), 2^m + 1) = d > 1$. Since $5 \mid 2^m - 1$, $5 \nmid d$.
 By (17),

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\chi}_{f_{a,b}^{(r)}}(0) &= \\ &= 1 + \sum_{u \in U} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(au^{r(2^m-1)})) \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{v \in V} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b(v\beta^i)^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}})) \\ &= 1 + d \sum_{u' \in U^d} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(au')) \frac{2^m-1}{5} \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\gamma^i)) \\ &= 1 + dh \frac{2^m-1}{5} \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\gamma^i)), \end{aligned}$$

where $U^d = \{u^d \mid u \in U\}$, $u \mapsto u^{r(2^m-1)}$ is a d to 1 morphism from U to U^d , $h = \sum_{u' \in U^d} \chi(\text{Tr}_1^n(au'))$. If $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is a bent function,

$$\widehat{\chi}_{f_{a,b}^{(r)}}(0) = 1 + dh \left(\frac{2^m-1}{5} \right) \sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\gamma^i)) = \pm 2^m.$$

By Lemma 2,

(1) if $\sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\gamma^i)) = -3$, then $3dh = -5$ or $3dh(2^m - 1) = 5(2^m + 1)$.

(2) if $\sum_{i=0}^4 \chi(\text{Tr}_1^4(b\gamma^i)) = 1$, then $dh = 5$ or $dh(2^m - 1) = -5(2^m + 1)$.

Notice that $d > 1$, $5 \nmid d$, $3 \nmid 2^m + 1$, $(2^m - 1, 2^m + 1) = 1$, all of the above equations can not stand.

Above all, the results follow. ■

V. CONCLUSION

This paper considers the bent and hyper-bent properties of the Boolean functions $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ of the form $f_{a,b}^{(r)} := \text{Tr}_1^n(ax^{r(2^m-1)} + \text{Tr}_1^4(bx^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}}))$, where $n = 2m$, $m = 2k \pmod{4}$, $k \in \{0, 1\}$, $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}$ and $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}$. When $m = 2 \pmod{4}$, we give a detailed description of the hyper-bent properties of $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$, and prove that the hyper-bent properties of $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ can be characterized by that of $f_{a',b'}^{(r)}$, where $a = a' \xi^i \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}$, $a' \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$, $b, b' = b\alpha^{-\frac{i}{r} \frac{2^n-1}{5}} \in \mathbb{F}_{16}$. We also prove that $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ is not a hyper-bent function unless $n = 12$ or $n = 28$ when $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^{\frac{m}{2}}}$. Further, we give all the hyper-bent functions for $n = 12$ or $n = 28$. When $m = 0 \pmod{4}$, we give a necessary condition for $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ to be a bent function. To those strict restrictions, it seems $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ can not be bent. In fact with the help of computer, we have checked all of the functions which satisfy Proposition 13 for $m = 4, 8$, and find that none of them is bent. Thus we guess when $m = 0 \pmod{4}$, $f_{a,b}^{(r)}$ can not be bent.

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